

Strategy for innovative development of the high-tech industrial complex of Russia in the context of globalization

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Аннотация. Инновационное развитие российского высокотехнологического производственного комплекса требует глобальной стратегии повышения качества продукции и использования возможностей современного глобального маркетинга. В статье рассматривается понятие глобальной стратегии, анализируется ее разработка зарубежными корпорациями и Роскосмосом, оцениваются преимущества и недостатки данных способов развития. Для формирования глобальной стратегии развития высокотехнологического производственного комплекса России предлагается системный подход, основанный на пяти важнейших принципах, сформулированных авторами.

Abstract. Innovative development of the Russian high-tech production complex requires a global strategy for improving the quality of products and using the features of modern global marketing. The paper examines the concept of global strategy, analyzes its development by foreign corporations and Roscosmos, and assesses advantages and disadvantages of these methods of development. The system approach based on the five most important principles formulated by the authors is proposed for forming a global strategy for developing the high-tech production complex of Russia.

Ключевые слова: глобальная стратегия, мировой рынок, конкурентоспособность, торговая политика, высокотехнологичный производственный комплекс.

Keywords: global strategy, world market, competitiveness, commercial policy, high-tech production complex.

Introduction

Since the second half of the 20th century, globalization is actively developing; its integral part is competition between states in various spheres, especially in the economy, where entire national industries actively compete. This puts new barriers to free entry into the global market, and to overcome the difficulties and to acquire and maintain competitive advantages, market participants begin to develop the so-called "global strategies" for national industries. Yet, some industries work better than others in the context of globalization, and individual countries have a significant advantage over other market participants.

In today's conditions of fierce competition and globalization, each component of the economic mechanism for the production and sale of innovative goods must be orientated towards the world market. At the same time, the economic strategy for the progressive development of this mechanism itself must become global. Global strategies are developed both at the micro level (firms and their associations) and at the macro level (entire industries and countries).

The term "global" (globalization, global strategy, global marketing) means that participants in world trade perceive the world as a single entity in which national borders and differences between buyers disappear [2]. Globalization allows manufacturing industries selling high-tech equipment to standardize their products, take advantage of the global marketing features, and thereby save on production scale

reduction. EADS, Boeing, Roscosmos, and other corporations are good examples of implementing a global strategy and organizing a global business. In terms of production scale, they combine entire industries. Such corporations manufacture similar products for different countries and occupy more than half of the world market.

Globalization forces us to significantly increase the innovation and quality of manufactured products. Since in modern conditions, simply copying the features of global trends does not gain competitive advantages, corporations must independently seek new markets and form their own commercialization and development strategies [4].

Main part

1. The concept of global strategy

Previously, the concept did not exist, the term "international strategy" being used in its stead. The international strategic option for different countries was created and implemented autonomously, and each country had its own strategy. Currently, the global manufacturing complex sells its products on a common global market, in which various states interact. Consumer demand is supported by marketing and sales tools and is satisfied by the supply and sale of a specific basic product.

The main concept of a global strategy is to identify common market characteristics and target consumer groups that do not depend on the characteristics of specific countries. In this case, regional and national advantages disappear, and customer demands and needs are globally aligned; due to the

standardization of goods sold, resources and finances are saved due to decreased production volumes [5]; firms and corporations actively use the advantages of global marketing; globalization strategy is based on probable advantage oriented toward consumers of cheap standardized products sold in local markets.

Thus, market globalization caused the same competing corporations to appear and trade in their national markets in various countries. These factors make global strategy particularly important. However, an undifferentiated market method is not always effective. Therefore, in practice, an average approach is often chosen, according to the following principle: differentiation in those markets where it is necessary, and standardization where it is possible. Consequently, the key goal of global strategy is standardization of goods and services sold. Corporations try to optimize the results of their market activities. Therefore, some markets allow deviations from optimal production principles.

Global strategy involves adapting the goals of the manufacturing industry and its available resources to the opportunities of the global market. Therefore, market entities are forced to master and develop global marketing, and to effectively use the opportunities provided to increase the number of buyers of their products and accelerate economic growth, as well as to protect against possible ruin due to more competitive global entities capturing a market niche.

2. Methods of developing a global competitive strategy

Developing and applying a global strategy is especially important for fully using all the opportunities and advantages of the industry. At the same time, refusal to enter the global market leads to the loss of place in the national (domestic) market. Most notably, business globalization leads to significant competitive advantages which can manifest themselves in the expansion of warehouse complexes, in access to new financial and raw materials, as well as in other factors that reduce production costs compared to the costs of competitors.

Thus, an industry global strategy:

- is a general, rather than detailed, plan for a certain industry, which covers a long period and a way to achieve a given goal in the world market;
- defines and specifies the ways to implement the strategy of enterprises and corporations, and identifies scientifically based organizational and economic approaches that the industry will use in the world market in each strategic business area;
- indicates how the industry is to achieve success and competitive advantages in all strategic business areas;
- is a plan for each specific business area, for a separate strategic sphere of business;

In a multidisciplinary and diversified sphere, a clear example is a high-tech production complex (HTPC) which uses several competitive strategies to gain reliable competitive and long-term positions in a specific strategic sphere.

Despite the fact that the main purpose of a global competitively oriented strategy is to focus on the future, it simultaneously allows for effective management and organizational decisions to eliminate

the numerous contradictions that often arise between the real capabilities and goals of a market entity at a certain time and on a global scale. This is explained by the fact that competitive environment continuously forces it to meet constantly emerging new requirements, as well as to use global features in its own interests while improving its market image and dominant characteristics in the world market.

The main purpose of a correctly formed and well-founded global competitive strategy is to choose a rational path of development, innovative methods of achieving the set goals, correct justification of the most promising types of production activities, the ability to occupy a very profitable and sometimes even unique niche in the market. Each participant in the global market creates and uses its own global strategy, taking into account the set goals and the characteristics of the world market. However, they all are to correctly assess their resources and capabilities, as well as take into account the periods planned for achieving the set goals, enhance their individuality, and achieve victories over their competitors in the same market. Although a global strategy allows achieving the planned goals, it does not fully guarantee them, since new factors are constantly appearing in the competitive environment; the direction of impact and economic content of these factors are sometimes difficult to predict. Thus, a strategy of this type cannot always protect against instability and failures; even a well-founded strategy is not able to predict the directions and features of socio-economic development with absolute precision and quickly obtain all the planned results.

Notably, a global strategy may be appropriate in industries where manufacturers face strong external pressure and require cost reduction. This allows global market entities to sell a standardized product worldwide and take advantage of economies of scale, because they are able to establish mass production of a standard product that can be exported.

3. Formation of global strategies by foreign corporations and Roscosmos

Global strategies require manufacturers to closely coordinate their production and pricing strategies in international markets. Therefore, entities that use a global strategy are, as a rule, highly centralized.

The effective management of any high-tech production is based on developing a strategy and adapting it to the specifics of a particular company and the features of practical implementation [1, 11]. A global strategy for a market entity is a comprehensive management plan that is to strengthen its position in the market and ensure coordination of efforts, attraction and satisfaction of consumers, successful competition and achievement of global goals. Strategy development is based on a thorough study of all possible areas of activities development and consists of choosing a general development direction and methods of competition, objectively assessing the markets being developed, as well as attracting additional resources and using innovative business models. In other words, a global strategy means choosing a path of development and markets, and methods of competition and of doing business.

International monopolies develop and effectively apply global strategies [7]. Below are examples

of global strategies by successful entities in the global market for products and technologies of various purposes, which today include, for example, Boeing (USA) and EADS (Europe). In 2011, the share of these manufacturers accounted for 80% of the world market for aerospace products.

Boeing. The main stage in forming the Boeing Corporation global strategy was the creation of Boeing International in 2001. In addition to the US market, this corporation controls the work of enterprises in 70 countries and develops and implements a global strategy for modernization and development at the enterprises of these countries. Moreover, in each country of residence, this corporation, using the strategy, determines, improves and evaluates competitive opportunities and advantages in developing and accumulating intellectual resources, develops business and expands partnerships. The mission and goals of the global strategy of Boeing Corporation provide for leadership in the aerospace industry.

The main provisions of this global strategy are intended to master new promising types and areas of production activities, to use the technical and technological achievements of the company in creating and manufacturing breakthrough innovative products and services, in ensuring sustainable stability of the main directions and forms of business.

The key principles of the strategy are as follows: lean production, system integration and implementation of complex large-scale projects, detailed and thorough study and fulfillment of all customer requirements taking into account their interests.

EADS. The European global aerospace corporation was created when the Spanish company CASA, the French company Aerospatiale-Matra and the German company Daimler-Benz Aerospace AG merged in July 2000. Next, the company Eurocopter (a subsidiary of EADS) acquired the Canadian company Vector Aerospace in June 2011, and in August 2011 the company Astrium (also a subsidiary of EADS) bought the investment fund Apax France from the company Vizada.

The global strategy of EADS is based on leaning on the support of strategic partners to obtain a solid position in the global market.

Provisions of the global strategy: a balanced type structure of products sold; a 10% to 25% increase in profitability from after-sales service; expansion of production and service networks beyond national borders; compliance with and improvement of environmental standards in relation to production and the products themselves.

Key principles: ensuring the integrity and transparency of key processes; establishing industry standards in the field of business ethics and enterprise risk management; supporting innovations in production; ensuring a smooth and effective integration.

Values: highly qualified personnel; increased profitability, capitalization and cost of exported products; protection of existing state project programs during budget constraints.

Roscosmos State Corporation. The strategy development for the Russian space industry, set out in the Concept for Implementing the State Policy in the Sphere of Space Activities up to 2032, consists in protecting geopolitical state interests, strengthening

the national security and increasing efficiency and rationality of using space scientific and technical potential [8].

The most significant goals of the strategy: expanding mutually beneficial international cooperation and stimulating commercialization in the field of space activities; modernizing production and implementing an effective and high-quality industrial policy; improving the quality of space devices and the technologies used to create these; increasing the scientific, technical, economic, production and defense potential of the state, as well as obtaining and using new knowledge; innovatively developing space products and technologies and implementing these in production sectors of the national economy.

Notably, the existing national strategy for the innovative development of space production industry does not fully meet the requirements for a global strategy.

Its shortcomings are explained by: blocking the procedure for organizing a business corporation expanded by several joint ventures with the help of the form of state ownership, which limits the possibilities of organizing and developing global space production; weak commercialization of scientific and technical industry achievements; imperfect organization, economic and production structure of the space industry; lack of skills and experience in using marketing technologies; insufficiently complete and modern scientific, production and regulatory framework in the industry.

Thus, any global strategy is indisputably aimed primarily at the international market, and the structure must meet the needs and rules of this global market.

4. Global strategy for the HTPC development

The long-term strategy for the innovative development of the domestic HTPC is intended for the design and production of the latest models of innovative goods and technologies for various purposes by creating a competitive complex consisting only of Russian enterprises. This has acquired particular importance in the sanctions conditions, yet creating such complex at the beginning of the XXI century was complicated by prolonged crises in the Russian economy [9, 10].

Specificity of global competition in the field of products and technologies for various purposes is due to the characteristics of this type of product. Traditionally, this is the name for specific products, as well as scientific and technical information which can be applied with equal success for production of equipment used in various spheres and sectors of the economy.

Notably, the Russian HTPC is traditionally focused on government orders, while foreign corporations seek to minimize their dependence on it. Moreover, in the era of globalization, domestic corporations enter the world market without the skills to independently market their products, and are forced to compete with manufacturers experienced in this aspect [6].

The main objectives of this strategy are: creating an effective mechanism for successfully selling manufactured products on the world market; improving federal legislation and creating an information

and analytical legislative base; developing organizational and economic methods that accelerate scientific, technical and industrial progress; training highly qualified specialists; increasing and improving scientific research, design, production and personnel potential of the industry [3]; structurally reorganizing the HTPC and identifying priority areas for its development.

In modern conditions, a system approach is required to create an effective global strategy for competitive development of the Russian HTPC and to eliminate shortcomings; such approach involves developing a global strategy based on five key principles.

1. Creating a new organizational and legal system that allows the HTPC to successfully enter the world global market. When developing strategies, it should be taken into account that entering the global market can be with the help of exporting (direct or indirect) of innovative products, since it makes up approximately 10% of total international economic activity; of creating international strategic corporations designed to organize business communities in which several manufacturers participate (which allows for jointly solving the same problems and reducing risks and uncertainties while achieving a common goal); producing through franchising or under license, which allows being present on the world global market without additional capital investments.

2. Forming the production and commercial policy of the HTPC, which, taking into account the existing market conditions, is to be used on the global knowledge-intensive market. A thorough system analysis of this market is required here – before developing a global industry strategy, it is necessary to clearly define what market opportunities the HTPC has and whether they can help in obtaining the planned economic effect; what competitive advantages and features the main participants in the selected segment of the knowledge-intensive market have and what advantages and features does the Russian HTPC have on this market; what products and technologies the HTPC will enter the market with and what will the demand for these products manufactured for sale be.

3. Innovatively modernizing the research, technical, design and production potential of the HTPC using global achievements, designed to increase its competitiveness in the world market. It requires actively using the latest technologies and technical equipment in high-tech production (including various applications), as well as creating effectively operating financial, resource and other funds to increase production capacity.

4. Developing and legislatively approving progressive state programs and investment projects based on global experience to implement them in the HTPC. Work is to be organized in accordance with the global strategy for the innovative development of this complex; this will allow the HTPC to become not a local competitor in the high-tech market but a world leader in this production sphere.

5. Integrating the Russian legal framework, in accordance with which the HTPC operates, with the basic norms of international law to harmonize Russian legislation with legal documents of other coun-

tries to defeat competitors in the oligopolistic, politicized and strictly regulated global knowledge-intensive market.

For successful operation in the global market, organizational and economic production system of the HTPC RPC is to be formed based on the above principles. The global strategy has many competitive advantages, therefore, at present, the above principles of the systems approach are the basis for their achievement.

Conclusion

Since in Russia, manufacturing products and technologies for various purposes is a closed cycle, the system method for constructing a global strategy to develop the domestic HTPC suggested in this paper is relevant and practically significant for numerous sectors of the economy. The proposed systems approach will stimulate the dynamic innovative development of the domestic HTPC and of industrial production in general. The new production and commercial policy, improved and adapted to international legislation, modernized organizational and economic management mechanisms, additional programs and funds of state support will allow fundamentally improving the strategic competitive position and status quo of the HTPC complex in the global market of high-tech products. This version of the global strategy will allow to fully realize the scientific research, technical, design and production potentials of the HTPC and will give it the opportunity to quickly enter the world market as the largest manufacturer of new innovative and competitive products and technologies.

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